

A REVIEW ON GLP-1 RECEPTOR AGONIST – SEMAGLUTIDE

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ABSTRACT

Glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) RA have arosed as a major therapeutic class for managing type 2 diabetes mellitus and obesity, with semaglutide representing one of the most potent agents in this category. This review summarizes the key characteristics of semaglutide, including its drug description, pharmacodynamics, and pharmacokinetic profile, and outlines its mechanisms of boosting insulin release in response to glucose and slowing the rate at which the stomach empties and promoting significant weight reduction. Evidence from major clinical trials demonstrates robust improvements in glycemic control, cardiovascular risk markers, and body weight across oral (Rybelsus®) and injectable formulations (Ozempic® and Wegovy®). The review further discusses the safety profile of semaglutide, highlighting common adverse effects such as gastrointestinal disturbances, as well as rare but notable concerns including pancreatitis and gallbladder-related events. Drug interaction data are summarized, with emphasis on interactions mediated by delayed gastric emptying.

Additionally, the dosage forms, administration techniques, and storage requirements for Rybelsus, Ozempic, and Wegovy are examined to clarify practical considerations for clinical use. Benefits such as substantial weight loss, once-weekly dosing options, and cardiovascular advantages are weighed against limitations including cost, tolerability issues, and the need for long-term therapy. Overall, semaglutide represents a highly effective therapy for diabetes and obesity, though individualized assessment remains essential to optimize its clinical utility.

Key words: GLP-1 receptor agonist, Semaglutide, Rybelsus®, Ozempic® and Wegovy®

INTRODUCTION

According to data from the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) in 2024, 589 million individuals (ages 20 to 79) worldwide—or one in nine persons—have diabetes. Four out of five individuals with diabetes (81%) reside in nations with poor or moderate incomes. In 2024, 3.4 million people died from diabetes, one every six seconds. An estimated 252 million persons (43%) have diabetes but have not received a diagnosis. Nearly 90% of people reside in nations with poor and moderate incomes. One in five live newborns are impacted by hyperglycaemia during pregnancy.

The NCD Risk Factor Collaboration (NCD-RisC), an international consortium of health researchers, estimates that 880 million persons suffer from obesity, according to World Obesity Federation statistics from 2024. Obesity affects 159 million children and teenagers.

Effective treatment approaches are desperately needed given the scope and quick increase of both diabetes and obesity. One such treatment that has received a lot of interest is semaglutide. Novo Nordisk's semaglutide, a GLP-1 RA, has become a ground-breaking medication for people with obesity and diabetes. It promotes insulin release only when glucose is elevated, lowers glucagon levels, and slows the emptying of the stomach and enhances feeling of fullness by imitating the natural incretin hormone GLP-1. These strategies concurrently treat two key metabolic disorders by improving blood glucose control and causing clinically significant weight reduction.

In conclusion, semaglutide has a dual-front therapeutic promise by targeting both glucose dysregulation and excess body weight—two key components of "diabetes."

In India, Novo Nordisk introduced Rybelsus® (oral tablets) in January 2022, Wegovy® (subcutaneous injection) in June 2025, and Ozempic® (subcutaneous injection) has not yet been introduced.

The core ingredient, formulation and distribution, purification, and manufacturing method are all covered by Novo Nordisk's several patents for semaglutide.

DRUG DESCRIPTION

Drug name	Semaglutide
Chemical name	Modified analogue of GLP-1 peptide
Chemical formula	C ₁₈₇ H ₂₉₁ N ₄₅ O ₅₉
Molecular weight	4113.58 g/mol
Appearance	White to almost white hygroscopic powder
Half- life	Approximately 1 week
Absolute bioavailability	0.4-1%
Isoelectric point	5.4
BCS Class	Class IV (Low Solubility and Low Permeability)
Solubility	Soluble in water (>100g/L at pH 7 or above)

Semaglutide is an GLP-1 RA. The peptide backbone is generated through yeast fermentation. Primary reason semaglutide lasts longer is because it binds strongly to albumin, a feature achieved by altering the lysine at position 26 and attaching a hydrophobic spacer along with a C18 fatty di-acid. Additionally, semaglutide is altered at position 8 to offer stability against dipeptidyl-peptidase 4 (DPP-4) enzyme breakdown. To guarantee that just one fatty di-acid was attached, a little adjustment occurred at position 34. [1]

Structural formula:

Fig.5:Structural formula for semaglutide [2]

The semaglutide is approved by the USFDA under the trade names Ozempic®, Wegovy®, and Rybelsus®. Patients with diabetes (type 2), can enhance their blood-glucose management using the Rybelsus® tablet formulation of semaglutide. The Ozempic® injectable version is additionally authorized to minimize the risk of cardiovascular complications in adults both with irrespective of T2DM. Wegovy®, another injectable form of semaglutide authorized by the FDA, is indicated for controlling body weight in individuals who are overweight or obese.

MODE OF ACTION

A GLP-1 RA, semaglutide shares 94% homologous sequence similarity with human native GLP-1 [3]. Semaglutide attaches and stimulates the GLP-1 receptor, the primary physiological aim of endogenous GLP-1. GLP-1 is a naturally occurring hormone that influences glucose regulation through multiple actions mediated by GLP-1 receptors. Its ability to bind to albumin helps slow renal clearance and shields it from metabolic breakdown, is the main mechanism of protraction that gives semaglutide its extended half-life. Additionally, the DPP-4 enzyme stabilizes semaglutide against degradation. Semaglutide suppresses glucagon secretion and increases insulin production in a glucose-responsive way to reduces the level of blood sugar. Thus, glucagon production is suppressed and secretion of insulin is

enhanced when blood glucose levels are high. A slight retardation in stomach emptying during the initial postprandial period is also part of the process that lowers blood glucose.

Adenylyl cyclase is activated when semaglutide interacts to the Gs protein-coupled receptor GLP-1R, which raises intracellular concentration of cyclic AMP (cAMP), along with the activation of Protein kinase A (PKA), EPAC are two important downstream effectors that are activated by increased cAMP and cooperate to facilitate insulin granule exocytosis. [4]

Fig.6: Mechanism of action of semaglutide

PHARMACODYNAMICS

Individuals with type 2 diabetes, who got subcutaneous injection administered once a week of semaglutide injection over a 12-week period were the subjects of the pharmacodynamic evaluations detailed below. Patients treated with semaglutide injection were initially given lower dosages before being dose escalated to 1 mg every week.

Basal and after-meal blood glucose concentrations

Basal and after-meal glucose concentrations are lowered with semaglutide. When semaglutide injection 1 mg was administered to peoples with type 2 diabetes, compared with placebo, blood glucose levels after fasting dropped by 29 mg/dL (22%), 2-hour post-meal glucose reduced by 74 mg/dL (36%), and the average 24-hour glucose concentration fell by 30 mg/dL (22%).

Insulin Secretion

When semaglutide is administered to individuals with type 2 diabetes instead of a placebo, insulin release is enhanced during both the first and second phases.

Glucagon release

Semaglutide reduces the glucagon levels during fasting and after food intake.

Glucose-mediated regulation of insulin and glucagon

Semaglutide reduces elevated blood sugar levels by promoting insulin release & suppressing glucagon production when glucose levels are high.

Semaglutide didn't interfere with the reduction of connecting peptide in peoples with diabetes (type 2) / alter the counter-regulatory glucagon responses compared with placebo during induced hypoglycaemia.

Gastric emptying

By delaying early postprandial stomach emptying, semaglutide lowers the pace at which glucose enters the bloodstream after a meal.

Cardiac Electrophysiology

A comprehensive QTc study examined the impact of semaglutide delivered subcutaneously on cardiac repolarization. Semaglutide did not significantly lengthen QTc intervals at an average exposure level four times greater than the maximum approved dosage of RYBELSUS.

PHARMACOKINETICS

Absorption

Semaglutide's absolute bioavailability in subcutaneous injection is 89%. After one to three days, the optimum level of semaglutide is attained. Semaglutide administered subcutaneously in the upper arm, thigh, or belly results in a similar exposure. After administering once-week for four to five weeks, steady-state exposure is attained.

Semaglutide is co-formulated with SNAC in oral tablets, which helps semaglutide absorption subsequent to RYBELSUS oral delivery. The stomach is the major site of semaglutide absorption.

- **RYBELSUS (R1):** Oral doses of 3 mg, 7 mg, and 14 mg resulted in bioavailability of 0.4–1%.
- **RYBELSUS (R2):** Oral doses of 1.5 mg, 4 mg, 9 mg produced bioavailability of 1–2%.

About an hour after oral RYBELSUS administration, the maximal concentration of semaglutide was attained.

When combined with SNAC, semaglutide's oral systemic availability is improved by a factor of 100. SNAC is a derivative of small fatty acids that facilitates absorption through the stomach epithelium.

SNAC raises the localized pH surrounding the tablet and shields it from acidic pH and enzyme proteolytic destruction. It facilitates the GI epithelium's transcellular absorption of semaglutide. [5]

Fig.7: Absorption mechanism of semaglutide with SNAC

Distribution

Semaglutide and plasma albumin are more than 99% bound.

When semaglutide is administered subcutaneously to type 2 diabetes and obesity patients, the average apparent volume of distribution is around 12.5L.

An absolute volume of distribution is about 8 L when taking medication orally in type 2 diabetes patients.

Elimination

The half-life of semaglutide elimination is around a week.

When administered subcutaneously, semaglutide appears to be cleared by individuals who have type 2 diabetes at a rate of around 0.05 L/h.

Absolute clearance is about 0.04 L/hour while taking the medication orally in type 2 diabetes patients.

Metabolism

Semaglutide is mostly eliminated by metabolism when the peptide backbone is cleaved by proteases and the fatty acid side chain is subsequently beta-oxidized.

Excretion

Urine and faeces are the main excretion pathways for semaglutide-related

substances. Intact semaglutide makes up around 3% is eliminated in the urine.

Particular group of individuals

In specific populations, including adults aged ≥ 18 years, different sexes, races (White, Asian, Black or African American), ethnicities, body weights (40–188 kg), those with upper gastrointestinal conditions (such as persistent gastritis or gastroesophageal reflux disease), varying levels of liver diseases (mild to severe per the Child-Pugh classification), and kidney dysfunction (mild to end-stage renal disease), no clinically meaningful differences were observed in the pharmacokinetics of semaglutide. [6]

DRUG INTERACTION STUDIES

The absorption of concurrently administered oral medications may be impacted by semaglutide's prolongation of stomach emptying. Clinical trials used orally administered semaglutide at steady-state levels to investigate its potential effects on the absorption of other oral medications.

Levothyroxine: After a single dosage of 600 mcg of levothyroxine was given concurrently with oral semaglutide, the AUC of total thyroxine (i.e., corrected for endogenous levels) rose by 33%.

Other Drugs: When semaglutide and omeprazole were taken together, no clinically significant changes in semaglutide pharmacokinetics were seen. Concomitant consumption of semaglutide, digoxin, S-warfarin, ethinyl estradiol, R-warfarin, lisinopril, metformin, furosemide, levonorgestrel, or rosuvastatin did not result in any clinically relevant changes in the pharmacokinetics of these medications.

In Vitro Studies: Semaglutide's ability to block or stimulate CYP enzymes and drug transporters is extremely modest. [7]

ADVERSE REACTIONS

The severe adverse effects are given below:

- Risk of tumours in thyroid C-cells
- Acute pancreatic inflammation
- Problems from diabetes induced retinopathy
- Low blood sugar levels with simultaneous administration of insulin or insulin secretagogues
- Acute renal damage from fluid depletion [8]
- Severe gastrointestinal adverse events
- Hypersensitivity responses
- Acute gallbladder illness
- Pulmonary aspiration under general anaesthesia or profound sedation [9]

CONTRAINDICATIONS

- Having MTC yourself or in your family or MEN 2 may be present in affected individuals.
- Previous allergic reactions to semaglutide or other excipients in the formulation. Anaphylaxis and angioedema are examples of severe hypersensitivity responses that have been documented. [10]

ADVISORY ON POTENTIAL RISKS

Risk of Thyroid C-Cell Tumour

Following lifetime exposure at clinically relevant plasma concentrations, semaglutide increased the occurrence of thyroid C-cell neoplasm (benign and malignant tumors) in mice and rats, with effects increasing according to dose and duration of treatment. Since the significance of semaglutide-triggered thyroid C-cell neoplasm in rodents hasn't been established, it is uncertain if semaglutide formulations produce thyroid C-cell neoplasm, thyroid medullary cancers, in people.

There have been reports of MTC in peoples receiving treatment with liraglutide, another GLP-1 RA, during the postmarketing period. However, the

information in these studies is inadequate to prove or refute a link between MTC and the use of GLP-1RA in humans.

In individuals using semaglutide, routine blood calcitonin monitoring or thyroid ultrasonography may not be beneficial for the early diagnosis of MTC. Because blood calcitonin has a low-test specificity and thyroid illness is quite prevalent, such surveillance may raise the risk of needless operations. Patients with medullary thyroid carcinoma frequently exhibit calcitonin levels above 50 ng/L and a significantly increased blood calcitonin value may suggest MTC. If a measurement of serum calcitonin reveals an increased level, the patient has to be assessed further. Individuals who have thyroid nodules detected by neck imaging or physical examination should also undergo further testing. [11]

TOXICITY

Severe nausea, vomiting, and hypoglycaemia may result from an oral or subcutaneous semaglutide overdose.

SNAC and oral semaglutide are frequently used together to improve stomach absorption. Research on animals has shown that increased exposure to SNAC can cause ataxia, decreased activity, irregular breathing, and lethargy.

Chronic weight management:

The Semaglutide Treatment Effect in People with Obesity (STEP) program comprehensively assessed the impact of once-weekly subcutaneous semaglutide administration (Wegovy®) on reduction in body weight in adults with obesity (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²) or overweight (BMI ≥ 27 kg/m²) with associated comorbidities. Based on the positive outcomes observed in four STEP trials, the FDA has approved, adults who are obese, or overweight with conditions like high blood pressure or type 2 diabetes, can use a weekly 2.4 mg injection of semaglutide to help manage their weight long-term (STEPs 1, 2, 3, and 4).

Semaglutide should be administered alongside a balanced diet and regular physical activity as part of the suggested weight management strategy. Subcutaneous weekly semaglutide (Wegovy®) was found to be superior than subcutaneous daily liraglutide in the STEP 8 study. The study's main endpoint was average body weight change (%) another active comparative trial.

STEP TEENS study evaluated how well semaglutide works and its safety against a placebo in obese teenagers between the ages of 12 and under 18. According to this study, teenagers' BMI was reduced more effectively by taking semaglutide subcutaneously (2.4 mg) injection every week in combination with changes in the lifestyle than by placebo and lifestyle changes alone. [12]

POSTMARKETING EXPERIENCE

When using semaglutide after approval, the following side effects have been documented. Accurately determining the incidence of these events or establishing a causal relationship with the drug is often difficult, since they are voluntarily submitted by individuals from a population of indeterminate size.

- Gastrointestinal: Acute pancreatitis and necrotizing pancreatitis, which can occasionally be fatal; intestinal, ileus blockage, severe constipation
- Hypersensitivity reactions may include anaphylaxis, angioedema, rash, and hives (urticaria)
- Liver and gallbladder issues may include cholecystitis and cholelithiasis, which may require cholecystectomy.
- Nervous system disorders may include headache, abnormal sensations (dysesthesia), altered taste (dysgeusia), and dizziness."
- Pulmonary: Use of GLP-1 RA in peoples undergoing elective procedures with deep sedation or general anaesthesia has been

associated with pulmonary aspiration.

- Renal: Acute renal damage
- skin and subcutaneous tissue: Alopecia

RYBELSUS®

DOSAGE FORMS AND STRENGTH

Formulation R1:

- Active ingredient: Semaglutide 3 mg, 7 mg, 14 mg per tablet
- Inactive ingredients:
 - Magnesium stearate
 - Microcrystalline cellulose
 - Povidone
 - SNAC

Formulation R2:

- Active ingredient: Semaglutide 1.5 mg, 4 mg, or 9 mg per tablet
- Inactive ingredients:
 - SNAC
 - Magnesium stearate

DOSAGE AND ADMINISTRATION

RYBELSUS is available in 2 distinct formulations: R1 and R2, have differing suggested doses. There is no mg-per-mg substitution for these formulations. Make use of RYBELSUS formulation R1 or R2. The two formulas should not be used together. No more than one pill should be taken each day.

RYBELSUS should be taken with water (up to 4 ounces) in the morning on an empty stomach. RYBELSUS should not be taken with any beverages other than water. Don't eat, drink, or take any other oral drugs for at least half an hour after taking RYBELSUS. Take pills whole. Do not chew, split, or crush. The next dosage should be taken the next day if a dose is missed. [13]

RECOMMENDED DOSAGE

RYBELSUS (formulation R1)

Reducing the chance of GI side events, suggest the following dose for RYBELSUS (formulation R1).

Starting Dosage (Phase of Initiation):

From 1 to 30: 3 mg taken orally once day is the suggested beginning dose (this dosage is ineffective for glycaemic management).

Upkeep and Escalation Dosage (Days 31 and beyond):

- Raising the dose to 7 mg orally daily once between Days 31 and 60.
- On Day 61 or beyond, keep the dose at 7 mg orally daily once if no further management of blood glucose is required. If more blood sugar control is required, up the dose to 14 mg taken once a day.

Formulation - R2

Suggested actions include RYBELSUS (R2) dose to lower the possibility of unpleasant gastrointestinal effects

Initiation Phase (Starting Dosage):

1 to 30 days: 1.5 mg taken once day is the suggested first dose; however, this amount is ineffective for glycaemic management.

Escalation and upkeep Dosage (Day 31& beyond):

- From Day 31 to Day 60: Raise the dosage to 4 mg taken once a day.
- After Day 61, if no further glycaemic management is required, keep the dose at 4 mg taken once a day. If further glycaemic management is required, the dose should be raised to 9 mg taken daily once.

STORAGE AND HANDLING

- Keep the product stored at 68°F to 77°F, with short-term temperature

variations allowed between 59°F and 86°F.

- Maintain the product in its original container for both storage and dispensing.
- Store in a dry environment, away from any moisture.

OZEMPIC®

OZEMPIC is an aqueous, sterile, clear, and colorless solution.

- Pen strengths: Each 3 mL prefilled, single-patient-use pen contains:

2 mg semaglutide	0.68 mg/mL
4 mg semaglutide	1.34 mg/mL
8 mg semaglutide	2.68 mg/mL

- Inactive ingredients (per 1 mL):

Disodium phosphate dihydrate	1.42 mg
Propylene glycol	14 mg
Phenol	5.5 mg
Water for injection	

- Additional information:
 - pH is approximately 7.4.
 - HCL or NaOH may be added to adjust pH.

DOSE AND STRENGTHS

OZEMPIC comes as a colorless, clear injection in 3 prefilled, single-use pens designed for one patient.

Each OZEMPIC pen contains a different concentration depending on the dose. For example, the 0.25–0.5 mg dose has 0.68 mg per mL, the 1 mg dose has 1.34 mg per mL, and the 2 mg dose has 2.68 mg per mL.

DOSAGE AND ADMINISTRATION

- Before using OZEMPIC, examine it visually. It should look colorless and transparent. OZEMPIC should

not be used if coloring and particle materials are visible.

- OZEMPIC should be given once per week, on a consistent day, at any hour, regardless of food.
- OZEMPIC injected subcutaneously into the thigh, upper arm or belly. When injecting in the same area of the body, advise patients to switch up the injection location every week.
- Patients should be instructed to give OZEMPIC and insulin separately and to never combine the two medicines. Insulin and OZEMPIC can be injected into in the same general area, but avoid injecting in adjacent spots.
- The weekly dose can be rescheduled if needed, as long as at least two days (more than 48 hours) pass between injections.
- OZEMPIC should be taken promptly feasible in the next 5 days after the missing dosage. If you miss a dose, move on to the next dose on the regularly scheduled day if more than five days have gone by. Patients can then return to their usual once-weekly dose regimen in each scenario.

RECOMMENDED DOSAGE

Recommended Initiation Dosage

Start administering OZEMPIC subcutaneously once a week for four weeks at a dose of 0.25 mg. To lower the chance of unpleasant gastrointestinal effects, adhere to the dose escalation listed below. Raise the dose to 0.5 mg once in a week after 4 weeks on the 0.25 mg dosage.

Recommended Maintenance and Maximum Dosages for Glycaemic Control

Depending on glycaemic control, a subcutaneous injection of 0.5 mg, 1 mg, or

2 mg weekly once is the suggested on going dose. If further glucose management is required following at least four weeks on the:

- Once a week, the dose can be raised from 0.5 mg to 1 mg.
- Once in a week, the dose can be raised from 1 mg to 2 mg.

A weekly dose of no more than 2 mg is advised.

Maintenance Therapy Recommendation for Individuals with Diabetes (Type 2) and chronic kidney disease:

Following a minimum of 4 weeks on the 0.5 mg dose, raise it to the maintenance dosage of 1 mg weekly once. [14]

STORAGE AND HANDLING

- Before the first use, OZEMPIC must be refrigerated at 36°F to 46°F. Do not store the product in the freezer or in direct contact with the refrigerator's cooling element. Freezing is prohibited, and the product must not be used if it is frozen.
- After the OZEMPIC pen has been activated for the first time, it may be stored for up to 56 days either at room temperature (59°F to 86°F) or in the refrigerator (36°F to 46°F). Do not freeze. Keep the pen capped and away from heat or sunlight.
- Discard the needle after each use, store the pen needle-free, and use a new needle every time.

WEGOVY®

WEGOVY is an aqueous, sterile, clear, and colorless solution.

- Single-dose pens:
 - 0.5 mL pens contain 0.25 mg, 0.5 mg, or 1 mg of semaglutide.
 - 0.75 mL pens contain 1.7 mg or 2.4 mg of semaglutide.

- Inactive ingredients (per 1 mL):

Disodium phosphate dihydrate	1.42 mg
Sodium chloride	8.25 mg
Water for injection	As required

- Additional information:
 - WEGOVY has a pH of approximately 7.4.
 - HCL or NaOH may be used to adjust the pH.

DOSAGE FORMS AND STRENGTHS

WEGOVY comes as a clear, colorless injection in 5 prefilled, single-use pens:

- 0.25 mg, 0.5 mg, 1 mg (0.5 mL)
- 1.7 mg, 2.4 mg (0.75 mL)

DOSAGE AND ADMINISTRATION

- Prior to and throughout WEGOVY therapy, blood glucose levels should be monitored in peoples with type 2 diabetes mellitus
- Before starting WEGOVY, teach patients the right way to inject themselves. Complete administration instructions with images may be found in the Instructions for Use that are included.
- Before every injection, check WEGOVY visually. Use only clear, colorless, particle-free solutions.
- Combine WEGOVY with a lower-calorie diet and more exercise.
- WEGOVY should be administered every week, on the consistent day, at a convenient time, regardless of food intake.
- WEGOVY should be injected subcutaneously into the upper arm, thigh, or abdominal area. The injection site and timing can be varied without modifying the prescribed dose.

DOSAGE RECOMMENDED

Start WEGOVY with a subcutaneous injection of 0.25 mg weekly once. To lower the chance of gastrointestinal side effects, adhere to the suggested dose commencement and escalation. Consider postponing dosage increase for four weeks if patients are unable to tolerate a dose.

Initiation (Weeks 1–4): 0.25 mg once weekly

Escalation:

Weeks 5–8	0.5 mg once in a week
Weeks 9–12	1 mg once in a week
Weeks 13–16	1.7 mg once in a week

Maintenance (Week 17 onward): 2.4 mg once weekly

Recommended Maintenance Dosage

Lowering cardiovascular risk and promoting weight loss

- WEGOVY's recommended weekly maintenance dose for weight loss and lowering heart-related risks is 2.4 mg, or 1.7 mg given under the skin.
- Tolerability and treatment response are taken into account when selecting the maintenance dose.

Noncirrhotic MASH exhibiting moderate-to-advanced hepatic scarring

- In the management of noncirrhotic MASH with mild to severe liver fibrosis, a weekly subcutaneous injection of 2.4 mg WEGOVY is the suggested maintenance dose.
- If a patient is unable to tolerate the 2.4 mg once-weekly maintenance dose, it may be reduced to 1.7 mg weekly, with the possibility of re-escalating to 2.4 mg as tolerated.

Recommendations Regarding Missed Dose

- Give WEGOVY promptly after a missed dose only when the next dose is >48 hours from now. If the upcoming dose is due within 48 hours, do not administer the missed dose. Continue treatment on the patient's regular weekly dosing day.
- If two or more doses are missed in a row, resume the medication as directed, or restart the dosing schedule if needed.

WEGOVY and comply with the gradual dose-increase protocol, as this can decrease the risk of gastrointestinal symptoms upon reinitiating therapy.

STORAGE AND HANDLING

- Keep the WEGOVY single-dose pen refrigerated at 2°C to 8°C.
- If necessary, the pen may be stored at 8°C to 30°C for up to 28 days, as long as the cap has not been removed.
- Do not freeze the product, and keep it protected from light.
- Store WEGOVY in its original carton until it is ready to be used. Dispose of the pen after a single use.

BENEFITS OF SEMAGLUTIDE**1. Superior Glycaemic Control**

- Semaglutide significantly reduces HbA1c (up to -1.8%) compared with placebo and other antidiabetic agents such as sitagliptin, empagliflozin, and insulin glargine.
- Provides sustained glucose lowering with once-weekly (injectable) or once daily (oral) dosing.
- Improves both fasting and postprandial glucose levels through glucose-dependent insulin secretion.

2. Prominent Weight Reduction

- Demonstrates clinically meaningful weight loss in both diabetic and nondiabetic individuals.
- Weight reduction ranges from -4 to -6 kg (Ozempic/Rybelsus) and up to -15- 17% of body weight (Wegovy 2.4 mg).
- Reduces appetite, delays gastric emptying, and enhances satiety.

3. Cardiovascular Benefits

- Proven reduction in major adverse cardiovascular events (MACE) in patients with type 2 diabetes and high cardiovascular risk (SUSTAIN-6, PIONEER-6).
- Improves lipid profile and lowers blood pressure modestly.
- Shown to have favourable effects on heart failure and atherosclerotic risk factors.

4. Convenient Dosing Options

- Available in two formulations: Injectable (Ozempic, Wegovy) – once weekly and Oral (Rybelsus) – once daily with absorption enhancer SNAC.
- Long half-life (~1 week) allows flexible and patient-friendly dosing.

5. Low Risk of Hypoglycaemia

- Because its insulin release is glucose-dependent, semaglutide has a low risk of hypoglycaemia, especially when not combined with sulfonylureas or insulin.

6. Improves Metabolic and Quality-of-Life Parameters

- Reduces waist circumference, blood pressure, and triglycerides.
- Enhances energy levels and physical functioning, leading to better treatment adherence.

7. Evidence-Based Efficacy Across Multiple Populations

- Proven benefits in type 2 diabetes, obesity, cardiovascular risk reduction, and even paediatric obesity (STEP TEENS).
- Effective across ethnicities and age groups.

8. Long-Term Safety and Sustained Benefits

- Long-term studies (STEP 5, 104 weeks) confirm durable weight loss and metabolic benefits.
- Well-tolerated with predictable side effects (mainly gastrointestinal, mild and transient). [15]

DRAWBACKS OF SEMAGLUTIDE

1. Gastrointestinal Side Effects

- The most common adverse effects are nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, and abdominal discomfort, especially during the initial dose-escalation period.
- Usually mild to moderate but may lead some patients to discontinue therapy.

2. Risk of Gallbladder Disorders

- Weight loss and GLP-1 receptor stimulation can increase the risk of cholelithiasis (gallstones) or cholecystitis in some patients.

3. Contraindication in Certain Conditions

- Not recommended in patients with a personal or family history of medullary thyroid carcinoma (MTC) or Multiple Endocrine Neoplasia type 2 (MEN 2).
- Avoid use in patients with severe gastrointestinal disease (e.g., gastroparesis).

4. Possible Risk of Pancreatitis

- Rare cases of acute pancreatitis have been reported; patients should be advised to discontinue semaglutide if persistent severe abdominal pain occurs.

5. Injection-Related or Administration Burden

- Although dosing is convenient (weekly or oral), proper technique and timing (especially for oral semaglutide, which must be taken on an empty stomach with limited water) can be difficult for some patients.

6. High Cost and Limited Accessibility

- Semaglutide formulations (Ozempic, Rybelsus, Wegovy) are expensive and may not be covered by all insurance or national health programs.
- Cost limits accessibility, especially in low- and middle-income settings.

7. Weight Regain After Discontinuation

- When semaglutide therapy is stopped, partial weight regain often occurs, indicating the need for long-term treatment or lifestyle support.

8. Limited Data in Certain Populations

- Long-term data in pregnancy, lactation, and type 1 diabetes are insufficient. Use in paediatrics is approved only for obesity (Wegovy TEENS), not for diabetes yet. [16]

CONCLUSION

As a GLP-1 RA, semaglutide has recently gained prominence as a ground breaking

treatment option for type 2 diabetes mellitus and obesity. By improving glycaemic control and promoting significant weight reduction, semaglutide effectively targets two major components of metabolic syndrome.

Clinical evidence from large-scale trials such as SUSTAIN, PIONEER, and STEP confirms its superior efficacy and cardiovascular benefits compared with conventional treatments.

The introduction of both oral (Rybelsus®) and injectable (Ozempic®, Wegovy®) formulations offers flexibility and enhances patient compliance.

Overall, semaglutide represents a major advancement in the field of metabolic disease management, providing a dual-action approach that addresses hyperglycaemia and obesity simultaneously—paving the way for a healthier and more sustainable future in diabetes care.

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